

The Effect of Telework on Employee Performance and Job Stress Mediated by Work-Life Balance of the Sekotong Public Health Centre Employees

¹Rolandra Gistennang ; ²Thatok Asmony ; ³Siti Nurmayanti
Master of Management, Faculty of Economics and Business University of Mataram
Mataram, Indonesia

Abstract: This study aims to examine the effect of telework on employee performance and job stress mediated by work-life balance at the Sekotong Public Health Centre. This study uses a quantitative approach. The sample of this study was 64 employees of the Sekotong Public Health Centre. This study uses a perceptual variable that is measured through a questionnaire instrument. Therefore, the research data was obtained by assessing the research subjects through the questionnaire. The obtained data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis. This study found that telework has a significantly positive effect on performance and work-life balance, but has a significant negative effect on job stress. Work-life balance has a significant and positive effect on employee performance, but a significant and negative effect on job stress. Work-life balance also has a positive role as a mediator in the relationship between telework and performance, while also having a negative role in the relationship between telework and employee stress. The effect of job stress on employee performance is known to be significantly negative.

Keywords:- Telework, Employee Performance, Job Stress, Work-Life Balance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources play a major role that influences every activity carried out by the organization and is considered the spearhead for carrying out daily organizational activities. Organizations must be able to manage employees to improve organization performance. Managing employees is a great concern since they are a very significant factor and they function as the prime mover for the smooth running of the business and organizational performance. The utilization of employees requires serious thought, especially for organizations that employ a lot of human labor. Each organization must have behavior either written or unwritten standards that must be carried out. The organization wants its employees to comply with this behavior standard to improve performance. According to Mangkunegara (2005), performance is defined as the implementation of employee responsibilities by achieving quality and quantity standards appointed by the company.

There are some factors identified to affect employee performance, one of them that has often been studied by previous researchers is job stress experienced by employees. Job stress is excessive workload, feelings of distress and emotional tension that restrain individual performance. Job stress is a factor that determines the ups and downs of employee performance. Job stress can disrupt work concentration, unsatisfactory performance and individuals not being able to meet the demands of their work. Job stress causes deviations in the psychological, physical and behavioral functions of individuals, and this can cause deviations from normal functions (Robbins, Stephen, and Coulter, 2010). Several studies have shown that there is an influence of job stress on employee performance. The results of Arshadi and Damiri's research (2013) found a significant negative relationship between job stress and job performance. Then a study conducted by Jamal (2010) showed that job stress hurts employee performance. This research was conducted on public sector employees in Saudi Arabia.

Employee performance and job stress are influenced by many factors, one of which is information and communication technology. Advances in information and communication technology (ICT) such as computers or mobile devices have resulted in significant changes in organizational business practices in the last few decades (Fawziah and Irwansyah, 2020). Technology has made it easier for every employee to gain access to information and communication through the system. In addition, employees can share knowledge with other employees in real time anywhere. However, at the same time, they must still handle multiple tasks simultaneously (multi-tasking) and respond to work-related information in real-time (Ye, 2012). Technology is now the main support so that the operations of companies or agencies can run. Without technology, every worker cannot access information.

Related to these technological developments, there is a working system called telework. Telework means working using telecommunications technology for the benefit of a company by permitting all employees concerned to access various company data anywhere without requiring the employee to be physically present in the office (Ye, 2012). The existence of Telework has changed the work system from previously conventional to online. This makes every worker no longer bound by the place and hours of work that

have been set by the company. The benefits of implementing Telework itself are apart from flexible working hours, Ye (2012) explains that telework can increase employee productivity, improve the quality of communication between employees and customers, ensure a balance between employees' personal lives and work, and reduce costs. Fixed expenses for company operations such as electricity, telephone and building costs. A study conducted by Golden (2006) concluded that telework has positive and negative effects on employee performance. Another study conducted by Bloom, Liang, Roberts, and Ying (2015) concluded that telework has a positive impact on employee performance. A study by Tews, Gudmundson, and Skarlicki (2014) showed that telework can aggravate job stress levels. Another study by Raghuram and Venkatesh (2008) showed that telework can aggravate job stress levels due to the lack of separation between work and personal life. However, several studies also show that telework can have a positive effect on job stress if individuals have balanced time management and support from colleagues and superiors, one of which is the study by Duxbury and Higgins (2011).

Based on previous research, there are inconsistent results on the relationship between telework and employee performance as well as telework and job stress, so it can be assumed that there was a mediating variable between the effect of telework on employee performance and the effect of telework on job stress. We suggest the mediating one of the possible mediating variables is work-life balance. Berk and Gundogmus (2018) define Work-life Balance as organizational support for aspects of employees' personal lives such as work that has flexible hours, dependent care and family/personal leave. Accordingly, according to boundary theory, the boundaries between work and family are becoming increasingly blurred (Lautsch, Kossek, and Eaton., 2009), making it difficult to switch roles (work and personal/family life). Therefore, integration is suggested over segmentation to minimize burnout, maintain higher levels of job performance (Debora, Smith, and Johnson, 2014) and avoid conflict.

Consequently, telework contributes to better Work-life Balance since it increases autonomy, reduces stress (Dima et al., 2019), and also increases availability for personal and family matters (Thulin, Vilhelmson, and Johansson 2019). At the same time, several studies have found that telework is negatively correlated with Work-life Balance either because of the difficulties workers face in detaching themselves from work problems (Felstead and Henseke, 2017) or because of the resulting conflict by expecting work-related things to be done outside the usual schedule (Sarbu, 2018). Research by Obiageli, Uzochukwu, and Ngozi (2015) states that work-life balance and performance have a positive relationship. Mendis and Weerakkody (2017) stated that Work-life Balance has a significant impact on the work performance of employees. Bataineh (2019) states that Work-life Balance shows substantial positive results and significantly influences employee performance. Research conducted by Mmakwe, Anthonia, and Ukoha (2018) states that there is a strong positive correlation between work-life

balanced and employee performance. Previous studies regarding work-life balance and job stress were carried out by Haura, Tsalitsa & Etikariena (2020) highlighting that there is a negative relationship and significant conditions between Job stress and Work-life Balance, where higher Job stress will decrease Work-life Balance. On the other hand, the lower the Job stress will result in the higher the Work-life Balance.

Telework is expected to facilitate Work-life Balance since the work itself can be completed not only in the office but in other places as well to overcome boredom. Telework can also be applied to a place outside of the home (Ye, 2012). Research to examine the effect of telework on employee performance and job stress mediated by work-life balance hasn't been carried out, especially from the location that will be the focus of this research, specifically the Sekotong Public Health Centre located in West Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara, Indonesia. The performance of the Sekotong Public Health Centre shows that there were barriers to achieving success in the malnutrition program. There were always high numbers of cases of malnutrition in 2015-2018 so it can be said that there was a decrease in employee performance at the Sekotong Public Health Centre.

From the results of the evaluation, it was found that the Public Health Centre employees who served in the nutrition management program also concurrently held other tasks assigned by the head of the Public Health Centre. Another problem about it was when officers had to go to the field to make visits to residents' homes, the obstacle was that the residents' houses were located far away from the Public Health Centre which makes employees experience job stress. Based on the results of interviews with the employees of the Sekotong Public Health Centre, it was found that employee attendance was relatively good, but many employees arrived early and went home late after office hours. It is because they were obligated to input data which required them to be at the location where the community lived and it was far from the public health Centre. The inability of employees to manage work and family matters sometimes makes employees bored and eventually fatigue arises, which in turn causes employees to experience a decrease in performance. So that in 2019 one innovation was made, specifically the Smartphone Application Dr Sapto Anthro supports the Telework concept at the Sekotong Public Health Centre so that the staff can manage their attendance and fatigue levels of. The application was created in hopes that employees can be more optimal in providing services at the Sekotong Public Health Centre. Based on research gaps and phenomena at the Sekotong Public Health Centre, it is necessary to conduct more in-depth research related to "The Effect of Telework on Employee Performance and Job Stress Mediated by Work-life Balance at Sekotong Public Health Centre.

II. LITERATURE REVIEWS

A. Employee performance

According to Afandi (2018), performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in a company by their respective authorities and responsibilities to achieve organizational goals legally, does not violate the law and does not conflict with morals and ethics. Meanwhile, according to Farisi, Irnawati, and Fahmi (2020), performance is the result achieved by a person according to the standards that apply to the job in question. Based on those definitions, it can be concluded that employee performance is the achievement of employee results in a process of carrying out their duties according to the responsibilities given. Improving employee performance will have a positive impact on the company so that employees have a good and optimal level of performance to help realize company goals.

According to Davis in Mangkunegara (2017: 67), factors that influence performance achievement include ability factors and motivational factors. Employee capabilities consist of potential abilities (IQ) and reality abilities (knowledge and skills). Meanwhile, employee motivation is defined as the desire to do something that is given and to foster a sense of responsibility. Motivation is a condition that drives employees self-directed to achieve organizational goals (work goals) (Akbar, 2018).

Employee performance can be objectively and accurately evaluated through performance-level benchmarks. This measurement means providing an opportunity for employees to know their level of performance. According to Mathis and Jackson (2002:329). Employee performance indicators include:

- *Quality of Output*
- *Quantity of Output*
- *Timeliness*
- *Presence At Work*

B. Job stress

Job stress according to Hon and Chan (2013) can be defined as a psychological and physiological response that arises when work demands exceed a person's ability to cope or adapt. Job stress on employees can be defined as a condition of tension that affects one's emotions and way of thinking so that it can affect way of thinking when carrying out work. According to Robbins (2001), three main sources can cause stress, scilicet:

- *Environmental factor*
- *Organizational Factors*
- *Individual Factors*

According to Hon and Chan (2013), Job Stress has two indicators, including Challenge-related stress and Hydration-related stress. Challenge Related stress is a potential source of stress that can create stress for individuals but has a positive influence on individuals and organizations by stimulating creativity, increasing work

motivation, and job satisfaction and expanding learning opportunities through experience. Meanwhile, Hydrange Related stress is a potential source of stress that tends to create stress and has a negative influence because it drains individual resources and abilities excessively and or unexpected limitations prevent individuals from achieving valuable individual goals.

C. Work-Life Balance

Work-life balance gives employees the freedom to use their working hours to carry out personal activities such as family, hobbies, art, and studies, which do not only focus on work (Kim and Fortin, 2017). According to Weerakkody and Mendis (2017), Work-life balance is a work pattern that allows employees to combine employee responsibilities at work with other employee responsibilities such as caring for children or elderly relatives. Fisher (2013) states that Work-life Balance includes four important components as stated:

- *Time*
- *Behavior*
- *Tension*
- *Energy*

Hudson (2005) states that there are four indicators to measure Work-life Balance including:

- ✓ Work interferes with personal life. This indicator refers to the degree to which work can interfere with an individual's private life. For example, work can make it difficult for a person to manage time for his personal life.
- ✓ Personal life interference with work. This indicator refers to the degree to which an individual's personal life interferes with work life. For example, if an individual has problems in his personal life, this can interfere with the individual's performance at work.
- ✓ Personal life enhancements of work. This indicator refers to the extent to which a person's personal life can improve individual performance in the world of work. For example, if an individual feels happy because his personal life is fun then this can make the individual's mood at work enjoyable.
- ✓ Work enhancements of personal life. This indicator refers to the extent to which work can improve the quality of an individual's personal life. For example, the skills acquired by an individual at work can be used in everyday life.

D. Teleworks

Telework is synonymous with 'mobile work', 'remote work', and other similar phrases. Practically speaking, telework means someone doing work while not physically located at the head office/workplace (OljemarkSimon and LindénAdam, 2018). There are three dimensions of implementation or realization of telework proposed by Gadecki et al. (2018), scilicet:

- *Room: Transformation of the personal space of the house*
- *Time: The use of personal space by the work space that leads to a collision of two different time systems: cyclic time (housework) and linear time (professional work), which overlap.*
- *Social Roles: Narratives about oneself as a worker from home.*

According to Farrell Kathleen (2017), the telework indicator consists of:

- ✓ Flexible work environment.
- ✓ Stress Disorder
- ✓ Proximity to family
- ✓ Travel time
- ✓ Separation of home and office work and self-pressure.
- ✓ High creativity and productivity

E. Previous Research and Hypothesis Formulation

Gajendran and Harrison (2007) found that telework positively affects job performance, but it depends on work experience and flexibility. Meanwhile, Bloom et al. (2015) conclude that teleworkers have better performance and productivity compared to those who work in offices. Research conducted in Iran by Mirshekary, Akhavan, and Yazdanpanah (2016) shows that there is a positive effect between telework and employee performance. Correspondingly, Allen, Golden, and Shockley (2015) show that telework generally has a positive impact on performance and job satisfaction. The same thing regarding the positive effect of telework on employee productivity was also reported by Felstead and Henseke, (2017) Hopkins and McKay, (2019) and Houghton et al, (2018). Vega et al. (2015) found that remote workers feel that they can achieve higher levels of job performance because this modality provides more opportunities to concentrate on work tasks.

On the other hand, the research by Jackson and Fransman (2018) and Hadi et al. (2021) shows the opposite result. Based on Jackson and Fransman (2018), telework is negatively affected by family disturbances, social isolation, and reduced interaction with co-workers, so in the end, it cannot increase employee productivity. Meanwhile, based on Hadi et al. (2021), due to telework, there is a demand for homework which is positively correlated with emotional exhaustion, which in turn is negatively correlated with work performance. Based on the justification we found that there are inconsistent results regarding the relationship between telework and employee performance. This study aims to re-examine this relationship so that it can be formulated:

- *H1: Telework has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Sekotong Public Health Centre*

Golden (2006) shows that interpersonal relationships and social support can help reduce job stress in teleworkers. Especially if the employee feels less connected to their co-workers and superiors. Another study that discusses the negative relationship between telework and job stress is

Hill, Ferris, and Mårtinson (2003). Their research shows that telework can reduce job stress because it qualifies employees to have more time and flexibility in living their personal and family lives. In this regard, this study succeeded in strengthening the existing theory. But on the other hand, research by Gareis and Mackenzie (2017) shows that teleworkers have higher levels of job stress than employees who work in offices. Gajendran and Harrison (2007) in their research found that telework can reduce job stress by providing greater work flexibility and autonomy to employees. However, this study also found that telework can increase job stress by worsening the balance between work and personal life. Based on this explanation, there are inconsistent results regarding the relationship between telework and employee stress. This study aims to re-examine this relationship so that it can be formulated:

- *H2: Telework has a negative and significant effect on job stress at the Sekotong Public Health Centre*

Hill et al. (2001) explained that high-flexibility jobs are associated with better levels of work-life balance. In addition, Kim and Fortin (2017) show that telework can help reduce work-life conflicts caused by high job demands. Olson and Primps (1984) show that home-based work positively affects the quality of life, consequently contributing to work-life balance. It is supported by Nurmayanti, Sakti, and Rinuastuti (2022). However, several other studies have found that telework negatively affects work-life balance. It is due to the difficulties workers face in detaching themselves from work problems (Felstead and Henseke2017) or due to conflict by expecting work-related matters to be carried out outside the usual schedule (Sarbu, 2018). This conflict is more likely to occur in remote workers who have children, so the negative impact of remote work tends to be experienced by women. Based on this description, some studies show inconsistent results regarding the relationship between telework and work-life balance. This study aims to re-examine this relationship so that it can be formulated:

- *H3: Telework has a positive and significant effect on Work-life Balance at the Sekotong Public Health Centre*

Hosseini, Tarvirdzadeh, and Faraji -Rad's (2017) investigate employees in the manufacturing industry in Iran. The study concludes a significant positive relationship between work-life balance and performance. The same thing was stated by Onaolapo, Adegbesan, and Olaoye (2017) in their research on employees in the Nigerian banking industry. Hartati, Ardiani, and Utami (2019) also explained that Work-life Balance affects job performance mediated by job satisfaction. The positive impact of Work-life Balance on employee performance has also been discussed in Nisa and Nurdin (2020), Obiageli, Uzochukwu, and Ngozi (2015), Weerakkody (2017), Bataineh (2019), and Mmakwe, Anthonia, and Ukoha (2018). This study aims to re-examine this relationship so that it can be formulated: the impact of remote work tends to be experienced by women. Based on this description, some studies show inconsistent

results regarding the relationship between telework and work-life balance. This study aims to re-examine this relationship so that it can be formulated:

- *H4: Work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the Sekotong Public Health Centre*

Research by Michel et al. (2011) showed that work-life balance is also associated with negative impacts, such as burnout, stress, anxiety, depression and other health problems. In addition, Banwell's research in Alianto (2016) stated that with a high level of work-life balance, there might be a lower level of job stress. Vice versa, if the level of Work-life Balance is low, the level of Job stress will increase. In this regard, this study aims to re-examine this relationship so that it can be formulated:

- *H5: Work-life balance has a negative and significant effect on job stress at the Sekotong Public Health Centre*

Some previous studies discussed the direct role of telework on employee performance, such as Houghton et al. (2018) and Vega et al. (2015). In addition, there is research that shows a positive role of Work-life Balance on employee performance, i.e., Bataineh (2019). The relationship between telework and work-life balance has also been widely discussed in various research objects and locations, such as Barber and Jenkins (2013), Dima et al. (2019), Felstead and Henseke (2017), Hopkins and McKay (2019), Lautsch, Kossek, and Eaton (2009), Debora, Smith, and Johnson (2014), and Thulin, Vilhelmson, and Johansson, (2019). In connection with various previous studies that discussed the partial relationship between telework, work-life balance, and employee performance, this research will examine the relationship of these variables simultaneously whereas work-life balance acts as a mediator. Thus, it can be formulated:

- *H6: Telework has a positive and significant effect on employee performance mediated by Work-life Balance at the Sekotong Public Health Centre*

Several previous studies discussed the direct role of telework on job stress, such as Gajendran and Harrison (2007) and Golden (2006). Also, there is research that concluded the positive role of Work-life Balance on Job stress, i.e. study by Banwell in Alianto (2016). The relationship between telework and work-life balance has

also been widely discussed in various research objects and locations, such as Barber and Jenkins ., (2013), Dima et al. (2019), Felstead and Henseke (2017), Hopkins and McKay (2019), Lautsch, Kossek, and Eaton (2009), Debora, Smith, and Johnson (2014), and Thulin, Vilhelmson, and Johansson (2019). In connection with various previous studies that discussed the partial relationship between telework, work-life balance, and job stress, this research will examine the relationship of these variables simultaneously whereas work-life balance acts as a mediator. Thus it can be formulated:

- *H7: Telework has a negative and significant effect on job stress mediated by work-life balance at the Sekotong Public Health Centre*

Arshadi and Damiri (2013) found a significant negative relationship between Job Stress and performance. In addition, there is research by Jalagat (2017) which shows that work overload is significantly correlated with employee performance, and job stress is a problem that companies must consider so that employee performance becomes effective and efficient. Research conducted by Riane, Pio, and Tampi (2017) also revealed the same thing, namely that if the stress score is high, the performance score will be low, and the opposite is true. This study aims to re-examine this relationship so that it can be formulated:

- *H8: Job stress has a negative effect on employee performance*

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a quantitative approach, which involves measuring variables and testing hypotheses. This research was conducted at the Sekotong Public Health Centre located in Sekotong Tengah Village, West Nusa Tenggara Province, Indonesia. The subjects of this study were employees of the Sekotong Public Health Centre. The population of this study were all employees of the Sekotong Public Health Centre which includes 64 people. Due to the small population size, all subjects were taken as the research sample.

This study uses a perceptual variable that is measured through a questionnaire instrument. In connection with this, the research data was obtained from assessing the research subjects on the questionnaire. The research data obtained were then analyzed using descriptive analysis methods and Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis.

IV. RESULTS

A. Respondent Profile Description

This research was conducted at the Sekotong Public Health Centre involving 64 respondents. The profiles of the respondents are presented as follows.

Table 1 Respondent Profile Description

Characteristics	Category	Percentage (%)
Age	25 years and under	3.1
	26-30 years	23.1
	31-35 years	38.5
	36-40 years	15.4
	41-45 years	10.8
	46-50 years	3.1
	51 years and over	6.2
Gender	Man	35.4
	Woman	64.6
Marital status	Marry	87.7
	Single	12.3
Years of service	5 years and under	21.5
	6-10 years	53.8
	11-15 years	10.8
	16-20 years	7.7
	21-25 years	1.5
	26-30 years	3.1
	31 years and over	1.5
Work	Pharmacist/Pharmacist Assistant	3.1
	Midwife	24.6
	Doctor	6.2
	Physiotherapy	1.5
	Nutritionist	4.6
	Administrator	9.2
	Nurse	29.2
	Health Laboratory Officer	4.6
	Other	16.9
Last education	Junior high school	4.6
	Senior high school	12.3
	Associate degree	60.0
	Bachelor degree	23.1

Based on the table, it can be seen that most of the respondents who are employees of the Sekotong Public Health Centre belong to Generation Y. Generation Y is the group of people born in 1977-1994 (29-46 years old). The main characters from Generation Y have high self-confidence, are ambitious, are more open in dealing with change, and are used to gadgets. In addition, as many as six other people belong to Generation X, a group of people born in 1977-1994 (aged 47-58 years). Generation X has an independent character, prioritizes work-life balance, and is good at adapting. Furthermore, several respondents belong to Generation Z. Generation Z was born in 1995-2012 (aged 11-28 years) and has characters that are more literate in technology, easy to socialize with others, learn faster, and like the environment that supports them to grow, more creative, and full of challenges.

In addition, it is also known that there are many more female employees than male employees. Most of the employees are also married. Most respondents had been

employees at the Sekotong Public Health Centre for 6-10 years (53.8%). As for other employees, they even have work experience at the Sekotong Public Health Centre for more than 10 years.

The Sekotong Public Health Centre has 24.6% midwives, 29.2% nurses, and 6.2% doctors. One of these doctors is also the Head of the Public Health Centre. In addition, the Sekotong Public Health Centre only has a pharmacist and an assistant pharmacist. In addition, there is a physiotherapy officer, 3 nutritionists, 6 administrators in various matters (General, Finance, Pharmaceutical Warehouse, and Medical Records), and 3 Health Laboratory Staff. The other 11 people include cleaning services, cooks, medical recorders and health information, cashiers, health promotion, sanitarians and ambulance drivers. The majority of the employees have studied up to Associate and Bachelor's degree in fields appropriate to their respective jobs.

B. Description of Research Variables

The research data obtained from the 64 respondents were then analyzed to calculate the average score.

Table 2 Description of Research Variables

Variable	Average score	Category
Teleworks	3,40	Effective enough
Work-life Balance	3,44	High
Job stress	1.81	Low
Employee performance	3.52	High

The table shows that Telework at the Sekotong Public Health Centre is considered to be quite effective. In addition, Work-life balance is also categorized as good and the employee performance is high. On the other hand, the level of job stress for Sekotong Public Health Centre employees is still relatively low.

C. Outer Model

The outer model is evaluated through three aspects, namely (1) Convergent validity by evaluating AVE; (2)

Internal Consistency by evaluating Alpha Cronbach; and (3) Discriminant Validity by evaluating Cross Loading. The table shows that the measurement models of Telework, Work-life Balance, Job Stress, and Employee Performance have met convergent validity, internal consistency, and discriminant validity. Telework variables are significantly measured by the indicators Flexible work environment, Tim, Stress Disorder, Closeness to family, Creativity and productivity, also Time and Travel.

Table 3 Outer Model Evaluation

Variable	AVE	Alpha Cronbach	Cross loading
Teleworks	0.829 (significant)	0.958 (reliable)	6 valid indicators
Work-life Balance	0.778 (significant)	0.905 (reliable)	4 valid indicators
Job stress	0.764 (significant)	0.897 (reliable)	2 valid indicators
Employee performance	0.745 (significant)	0.661 (reliable)	4 valid indicators

The Work-life Balance variable is significantly measured by indicator Work interference with personal life, Personal life interference with work, Work enhancement of personal life, and Personal life enhancements of works. Variable Employee performance is significantly measured by the Quality indicator of output, Quantity of output, Timelines, and Presence at work. Finally, the variable Job Stress is significantly measured by the indicators Challenge-related stress and Hydration-related stress.

D. Inner Model

The inner model contains the results of testing the research hypothesis including path coefficients and p-values.

Table 4 Research Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis	Path Coefficient	P- value	Decision
H1	0.226	0.008	Significant
H2	-0.332	0.012	Significant
H3	0.873	0.000	Significant
H4	0.408	0.000	Significant
H5	-0.385	0.002	Significant
H6	0.624	0.000	Significant
H7	-0.336	0.003	Significant
H8	-0.401	0.000	Significant

➤ Visually, the Results of the Analysis Presented in Table 4 can be Seen in Figure 1 below.

Fig 1 Research Hypothesis Test Results

Based on these results, it can be seen that in all hypotheses have p-value is lower than the 0.05 significance level. Thus, the entire research hypothesis is accepted. The direction of the relationship between telework on employee performance, telework on work-life balance, work-life balance on employee performance, and telework on employee performance mediated by work-life balance, are all positive. On the other hand, the relationship of telework to job stress, work-life balance to job stress, telework to job stress mediated by work-life balance, and job stress to employee performance has a negative relationship.

V. DISCUSSIONS

A. The Effect of Telework on Employee Performance at the Sekotong Public Health Centre

The results found that effective teleworking will increase then employee performance. Conversely, ineffective teleworking will lead to decreasing employee performance. Hypothesis testing is also supported by empirical conditions shown through the description of research variables. Based on the variable description, the average respondent's answer to the telework variable is 3.403 and is included in the quite effective category. This can be interpreted that teleworking at the Sekotong Public Health Centre, which is using a smartphone application to input data, has been quite effective.

The measuring of the Telework variable is quite effective (almost reaching the effective category), also closely related to the respondent's profile. Most of the Sekotong Public Health Centre employees are Generation Y (29-46 years old) and they tend to be open to change and are familiar with gadgets. Hence, they also tend to be ready for teleworking. Additionally, most of the employees also have

quite a long working experience (more than five years) so they are also better prepared to deal with various conditions in their work. Regardless of the character and work experience, the measurement of telework variables has not yet reached the effective category. This is related to the profession of most of the respondents as health workers with higher workload demands.

In line with quite effective Teleworking, the average respondent's answer to this employee performance variable is 3.525 and is included in the High category. This can be interpreted that the employees' performance at the Sekotong Public Health Centre has been relatively good. The results of measuring the high employee performance variable are also closely related to the respondent's profile. Sekotong Public Health Centre employees are dominated by Generation Y (aged 29-46 years) with a character that tends to be ambitious at work. In addition, each employee has an educational background which appropriate to their profession, and most of them have more than five years of experience. This helps them to do their job well.

The findings of this study are in line with several previous studies conducted on various objects and different locations. The results of this study support the research of Gajendran and Harrison (2007), Bloom et al. (2015), Mirshekary, Akhavan, and Yazdanpanah (2016), and Allen, Golden, and Shockley (2015). This study also found that the advantages of telework, according to employees of the Sekotong Public Health Centre, are related to a comfortable place to work, not excessively tiring, saving time, and allowing them to calm down. This is in line with Vega et al. (2015) research. Regardless, this study is in contrast to the study of Jackson and Fransman (2018) and Hadi et al. (2021).

B. The Effect of Telework on Job stress at the Sekotong Public Health Centre

The results found that more effective teleworking will lead to lower job stress. On the other hand, more ineffective teleworking will cause higher job stress. The hypothesis is also supported by empirical conditions shown through the aligned description of the research variables. Based on the variable description, the average respondent's answer to the Telework variable is 3.403 and is included in the quite effective category. This can be interpreted that teleworking at the Sekotong Public Health Centre, which is using a smartphone application to input data, has been quite effective.

Contrary to Telework which is considered quite effective, the average respondent's answer to the Job Stress variable is 1.811 and is included in the Low category. This can be interpreted that job stress at the Sekotong Public Health Centre is relatively low. It is also closely related to the respondent's profile. The employees of the Sekotong Public Health Centre have an educational background appropriate to their profession, and most of them even have work experience of more than five years. Therefore, Sekotong Public Health Centre employees can do their jobs well without having excessive stress.

The findings of this study are consistent with several previous studies conducted on different objects and locations, namely Golden (2006) and Hill, Ferris, and Mårtinson (2003). On the other hand, the results of this study contradict the research of Gareis and Mackenzie (2017) and Gajendran and Harrison (2007).

C. The Effect of Telework on Work-life Balance at the Sekotong Public Health Centre

The results found that more effective Teleworking will lead to an increase in Work-life Balance. Conversely, more ineffective Teleworking will decrease the Work-life Balance. Thus, the third hypothesis is accepted. It is also supported by empirical conditions shown through the results of the description of the research variables. Based on the results, the average respondent's answer to the Telework variable is 3.403 and is included in the quite effective category. It means that teleworking at the Sekotong Public Health Centre, which is using a smartphone application to input data, has been quite effective.

In line with this, the average respondent's answer to the Work-life Balance variable is 3.438 and is included in the High category. This can be interpreted that the work-life balance at the Sekotong Public Health Centre is relatively good. It is closely related to the respondent's profile. The majority of employees at the Sekotong Public Health Centre are married. In this regard, married employees tend to set aside time to gather and enjoy time with their families. In addition, they also have higher motivation to work. Therefore, it is only natural that employees at the Sekotong Public Health Centre have a high work-life balance.

The findings of this study are in line with several previous studies conducted on various objects and different locations, including the research by Hill et al. (2001), Kim and Fortin (2017), Olson and Primps (1984), and Nurmayanti, Sakti, and Rinuastuti (2022). This research contradicts the research of Felstead and Henseke (2017) and Sarbu (2018).

D. Effect of Work-life Balance on Employee Performance at the Sekotong Public Health Centre

The results found that better Work-life Balance will increase employee performance. Conversely, a worse Work-life Balance will lead to a decrease in the employee's performance. It is supported by empirical conditions that show the average respondent's answer to the Work-life Balance variable is 3.438 and included in the High category. In line with the Work-life Balance which is considered high, the average respondent's answer to the employee performance variable is 3.525 and also included in the High category.

The findings of this study are in line with several previous studies conducted on various objects and different locations. One of them is research conducted by Hosseini, Tarvardizadeh, and Faraji -Rad (2017) on employees in the manufacturing industry in Iran. The study found a significant positive relationship between work-life balance and performance. The same thing was expressed by Onaolapo, Adegbesan, and Olaoye (2017) in their research on employees in the Nigerian banking industry. Hartati, Ardiani, and Utami (2019) in their research on nurses explained that Work-life Balance affects job performance mediated by job satisfaction. The positive effect of Work-life Balance on employee performance has also been discussed by Nisa and Nurdin (2020), Obiageli, Uzochukwu, and Ngozi (2015), Weerakkody (2017), Bataineh (2019), and Mmakwe, Anthonia, and Ukoha (2018). In this regard, this study succeeded in strengthening the existing theory.

E. Effect of Work-life Balance on Job stress at the Sekotong Public Health Centre

The results also show that a better work-life balance will lower job stress. Conversely, a worse Work-life Balance will lead to higher Job stress. It is supported by empirical conditions shown through the descriptive. Based on the table, the average respondent's answer to the Work-life Balance variable is 3.438 and is included in the High category. Contrary to the considered high Work-life balance, the average respondent's response to this variable is 1.811 and is included in the Low category. It is aligned with several previous studies conducted on various objects and different locations, namely Michel et al. (2011) and Banwell in Alianto (2016).

F. The Effect of Telework on Employee Performance mediated by Work-life Balance at the Sekotong Public Health Centre

The results found that effective Teleworking will increase Work-life Balance, which in turn will also improve employee performance. Hypothesis testing is also supported by empirical conditions. Based on the table, the average

respondent's answer to the Telework variable is included in the quite effective category. Meanwhile, the variables Work-life Balance and employee performance are included in the high category.

This research produces new findings and strengthens previous research which partially discusses the relationship between variables. This study reveals the important role of Work-life Balance, not only in directly influencing employee performance but also as a liaison (mediation) in the relationship between Telework and Employee Performance. With a Work-life Balance, the positive influence of Telework on Employee Performance can be increased. Thus, if telework increases, it will also increase work-life balance, which in turn will further increase employee performance.

G. The effect of telework on job stress mediated by work-life balance at the Sekotong Public Health Centre

The results found that more effective teleworking will lead to increased work-life balance and proceed to decrease job stress. It is supported by empirical conditions. Based on the description, the average respondent's responses to the Telework variable are included in the quite effective category. In addition, Work-life Balance is also included in the high category. On the other hand, job stress is in the low category.

This research produces new findings and strengthens previous research which partially discusses the relationship between variables. This study reveals the important role of Work-life Balance, not only in directly influencing employee performance but also as a liaison (mediation) in the relationship between Telework and Employee Performance. With a Work-life Balance, the negative effect of Telework on Job stress can be increased. Thus, if telework increases, it will also increase work-life balance, which will further reduce job stress.

H. Effect of Job Stress on Employee Performance at the Sekotong Public Health Centre

The results found higher job stress will lower the employee's performance. Conversely, lower job stress will lead to increases in employee performance. The results of the hypothesis testing are also supported by empirical conditions which are shown through the results of the description of the research variables that are aligned. Based on the results of the variable description, the average respondent's answer to the Job Stress variable is 1.811 and is included in the Low category. In contrast to Job Stress which is considered low, the average respondent's answer to the employee performance variable is 3.525 and is included in the High category. The findings of this study are in line with several previous studies conducted on various objects and different locations, namely Arshadi and Damiri (2013), Jalagat (2017), and Riane, Pio, and Tampi (2017).

VI. CONCLUSION

Telework has a significant effect on performance, job stress and work-life balance. The direction of the relationship between telework and work-life balance is positive, while the direction of the relationship between telework and job stress is negative. Thus, telework that is carried out effectively can improve employee performance and work-life balance, as well as reduce employee job stress.

Work-life balance has a significant and positive effect on employee performance, but a significant and negative effect on job stress. Therefore, a good work-life balance can improve employee performance and simultaneously reduce employee job stress.

Work-life balance also has a positive role as a mediator in the relationship between telework and performance, while also having a negative role in the relationship between telework and employee stress. Effective telework will lead to a good work-life balance, which will further improve employee performance and reduce employee job stress. The influence of job stress on employee performance itself is known to be significantly negative, where the lower the job stress on employees, the higher employee performance.

REFERENCES

- [1] Afandi P. (2018). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori, Konsep dan Indikator)*. Riau: Zanafa Publishing
- [2] Alianto, A. & Anindita, R. (2016). "Pengaruh Kompensasi dan Work-life Balance Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Dimediasi Stres Kerja". *Jurnal Universitas Esa Unggul*, 2(3), 1-18.
- [3] Allen, T. D. Golden, T. D. & Shockley, K. M. (2015). "How effective is Telework? Assessing the status of our scientific findings". *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 16(2), 40–68.
- [4] Andini, I. & Surjanti, J. (2017). "Pengaruh Work-life Balance dan Komitmen Afektif Terhadap Kepuasan Karir Pada PT. Sinar Karya Duta Abadi". *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen*, 5(3), 1–10.
- [5] Arikunto, Suharsimi. (2010). *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- [6] Arshadi, N. & Damiri, H. (2013). "The Relationship of Job Stress with Turnover Intention and Job Performance: Moderating Role of OBSE". *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 84, 706–710.
- [7] Barber, L. K., & Jenkins, J. S. (2013). Creating technological boundaries to protect bedtime: Examining work-home boundary management, psychological detachment, and sleep. *Stress & Health*, 4, 300-323.
- [8] Baruch, Y. (2000). "Teleworking: Benefits and Pitfalls as Perceived by Professionals and Managers". *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 15(1), 34-49.
- [9] Berk, C. & Gundogmus, F. (2018). "The Effect of Work-life Balance on Organizational Commitment of Accountants". *Management*, 13(2), 137–159.

- [10] Bloom, N. Liang, J. Roberts, J. & Ying, Z. J. (2015). "Does working from home work? Evidence from a Chinese experiment". *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 130(1), 165–218.
- [11] Boell, S. Cecez-Kecmanovic, D. & Campbell, J. (2014). "Telework and The Nature of Work: An Assessment of Different Aspects of Work and The Role of Technology". *Twenty Second European Conference on Information Systems*, 1-15.
- [12] Carillo, L. R. Jin, Y. & Lai, K. K. (2020). "Developing and testing a Crisis-Induced Telework Adjustment Framework: Individual, job, and organizational factors as predictors of Telework adjustment". *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 105(11), 1238-1252.
- [13] Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods Approaches* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- [14] Debora, P. Smith, J. & Johnson, L. (2014). "The impact of digital media tools on remote work effectiveness". *Journal of Remote Work*, 10(2), 45-60.
- [15] Dima. A.M., Tuclea.C.E., Vrânceanu.D.M., and Tigu.G. (2019). Sustainable Social and Individual Implications of Telework: A New Insight into the Romanian Labor Market. *Sustainable Human Resource Management*.11(13), 3506.
- [16] Duxbury, L. & Higgins, C. (2011). "Flexible work arrangements: A source of job and life satisfaction or a source of role stress?". *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 16(2), 233-250.
- [17] Farisi S, Irnawati J, Fahmi M. (2020). Pengaruh Motivasi dan Disiplin Kerja terhadap Kinerja karyawan. *Jurnal Humaniora* Vol. 4.
- [18] Fawziah, S. A. & Irwansyah, I. (2020). "Telecommuting/Teleworking – Telework – Sebagai Solusi Efektif Mobilisasi Kerja". *Jurnal Infortech*, 2(1), 69–77.
- [19] Gajendran, R. S. & Harrison, D. A. (2007). "The good, the bad, and the unknown about Telework: Meta-analysis of psychological mediators and individual consequences". *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 92(6), 1524–1541.
- [20] Gareis, K. C. & Mackenzie, S. B. (2017). "Telework stress: An examination of coping strategies, job satisfaction, and social support". *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 32(7), 487–502.
- [21] Gibson, J. L. Ivancevich, J. M. & Donnelly Jr. (1996). *Organisasi: Perilaku, Struktur, Proses, Edisi Kedelapan Jilid Satu*. (Terjemahan Nunuk Ardiani). Jakarta: Binarupa Aksara.
- [22] Golden, T. D. (2006). "The role of relationships in understanding telecommuter satisfaction". *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 27(3), 319–340.
- [23] Gomez, F.C. (1995). *Sumber Daya Manusia*. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset.
- [24] Hartati, E. Ardiani, N. S. & Utami, P. N. (2019). "The Impact of Work-life Balance on Job Performance among Nurses in Indonesian Private Hospitals". *Enfermeria Clinica*, 29, 457-461.
- [25] Haura, Tsalitsa S, & Etikariena, A. (2020). "Keseimbangan pekerjaan dan kehidupan pribadi serta gaya kerja baru, bagaimana dampaknya terhadap Stres Kerja?". *Psycho Idea*, 19(01), 1–12.
- [26] He, S. Y. dan Hu, L. (2014). "Telecommuting, Income and Out of Home Activities Travel Behaviour and Society". Elsevier Ltd. on Behalf Of Hong Kong Society for Transportation Studies, 1-18.
- [27] Hill, E. J. Ferris, M. dan Mårtinson, V. (2003). "Does it matter where you work? A comparison of how three work venues (traditional office, virtual office, and home office) influence aspects of work and personal/family life". *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 63(2), 220–241.
- [28] Hill, E. J. Hawkins, A. J. Ferris, M. dan Weitzman, M. (2001). "Finding an extra day a week: The positive influence of perceived job flexibility on work and family life balance". *Family Relations*, 50(1), 49-58.
- [29] Hon, A. H. Y. & Chan, W. W. (2013). "The Effects of Group Conflict and Work Stress on Employee Performance". *Cornell Hospitality Quarterly*, 54(2), 174–184.
- [30] Hopkins, J. L., & McKay, J. (2019). Investigating 'anywhere working' as a mechanism for alleviating traffic congestion in smart cities. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 142, 258–272.
- [31] Hosseini, S. M. Tarvirdzadeh, H. dan Faraji-Rad, S. (2017). "The Relationship between Work-life Balance and Employee Performance: A Study of Iranian Manufacturing Industry". *Journal of Business and Management*, 19(2), 64-77.
- [32] Hudson. (2005). *The Case for Work-life Balance: Closing the Gap Between Policy and Practice*, 20:20 Series. Hudson Global Resources.
- [33] Jalagat, R. (2017). "Determinants of Job Stress and Its Relationship on Employee Job Performance". *American Journal of Management Science and Engineering*, 2(1), 1-10.
- [34] Jamal, M. (2010). Job stress, job performance, and organizational commitment in a multinational company: An empirical study in two countries. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5(3), 143-153.
- [35] Karatepe, O. M. (2018). "Work-life Balance and stress kerja: A literature review". *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 69, 24-30.
- [36] Kasmir, 2016. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori dan Praktik)*. Depok: PT. Rajagrafindo.
- [37] Kim, J. Y. dan Fortin, M. (2017). "Moderating effects of Telework on the relationship between job demands and work–life conflict". *New Technology, Work and Employment*, 32(1), 55–70.
- [38] Lautsch, B.A. Kossek, E.E, and Eaton, S.C. (2009). "Supervisory Approaches and Paradoxes in Managing Telecommuting Implementation," *Human Relations*, 62/6: 795-827.
- [39] Lilyana B, De Yusa V, Yutami I. (2021). Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja Fisik dan Kompensasi Non Finansial terhadap Kinerja karyawan Bagian Produksi pada PT. Rudant Maju Selaras. *Jurnal Manajemen Mandiri Saburai*.

- [40] Loh, L. dan Keng, C. J. (2019). "Factors influencing Telework adoption and continuance: A systematic review". *Computers in Human Behavior*, 101, 182-197.
- [41] Mangkunegara, A. P. (2005). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan*. PT. Remadja Rosda Karya.
- [42] Mathis, R. L., and Jackson, J.H. (2002). *Human Resource Management 10th Edition*. Ohio: Southwestern College Publishing.
- [43] Mendis, M. D. V. S. & Weerakkody, W. A. S. (2017). "The Impact of Work-life Balance on Employee Performance with Reference to Telecommunication Industry in Sri Lanka: A Mediation Model". *Kelaniya Journal of Human Resource Management*, 12(1), 72–100.
- [44] Michel, J. S. Kotrba, L. M. Mitchelson, J. K. Clark, M. A. and Baltes, B. B. (2011). "Antecedents of work-family conflict: A meta-analytic review". *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 32(5), 689-725.
- [45] Mirshekary, S. Akhavan, P. & Yazdanpanah, M. (2016). "The impact of Telework on job performance: The case of Iranian information technology organization". *International Journal of Information Management*, 36(6), 1236–1241.
- [46] Mmakwe, A. K. & Ukoha, O. (2018). "Work-life Balance and Employee Performance in Nigerian Banks, Port Harcourt". *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, 4(1), 107–119.
- [47] Nicholas, A. I. Obasi, J. & Anene, P. (2017). "The Influence of Job Stress, Commitment, Job Experience and Employees Performance in Selected Banks in Enugu". *Asian Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 1(9), 451–463.
- [48] Nilles, J. M. (1988). "Traffic reduction by Telework: A status review and selected bibliography". *Transportation Research*, 22(A), 301-317.
- [49] Nilles, J. M. Carlson, F. R. Paul, G. Jr. & Hanneman, G. J. (1974). "Development of policy on the Telecommunications-Transportation Tradeoff". University of Southern California and the National Science Foundation, Report NSF-RA-5-74-020.
- [50] Nisa, F. & Nurdin, N. (2020). "The Relationship between Work-life Balance and Employee Performance: The Mediating Role of Organizational Commitment". *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 9(6), 01-08.
- [51] Nurjaya N. (2021). Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja, Lingkungan Kerja dan Motivasi Kerja terhadap Kinerja karyawan pada PT. Hazara Cipta Pesona. *AKSELERASI: Jurnal Ilmiah Nasional* Vol. 3 No. 1.
- [52] Nurmayanti, S. Sakti, D. P. B. & Rinuastuti, B. H. (2022). "Pengaruh Work from home Terhadap Work-life Balance Pada Perempuan Bekerja Di Kota Mataram Di Masa Pandemi Covid-19". *JSEH (Jurnal Sosial Ekonomi dan Humaniora)*, 8(2), 306-311.
- [53] Obiageli, O. L. Uzochukwu, O. C. & Ngozi, C. D. (2015). "Work-life Balance and employee performance in selected commercial banks in Lagos state". *European Journal Research and Reflection in Management Sciences*, 3(4), 63–77.
- [54] Olson, K. R. & Primps, S. B. (1984). "The effects of home-based work on the quality of life". *Academy of Management Review*, 9(2), 267–277.
- [55] Onalapo, A. A. Adegbesan, J. A. & Olaoye, S. O. (2017). "The Impact of Work-life Balance on Employee Productivity: A Study of Nigerian Banking Industry". *Journal of Management*, 4(2), 15-25.
- [56] Perez, M. P. Sanchez, A. M. & Carnicer, M. P. (2002). "Benefits and Barriers of Telework: Perception Differences of Human Resources Manager According to Company's Operations Strategy". *Technovation*, 775-783.
- [57] Potter, E. (2003). "Telecommuting: The Future of Work, Corporate Culture, and American Society". *Journal of Labor Research*, 73- 84.
- [58] Raghuram, S. & Venkatesh, R. (2008). "The impact of Telework on Work-life Balance: An examination of mediating mechanisms". *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 25(2), 229-256.
- [59] Riane, A. N. T. Pio, J. & Tampi, D. L. (2017). "Pengaruh Stres Kerja Terhadap Kinerja karyawan Pada Pt. Bank Perkreditan Rakyat Dana Raya Manado". *Jurnal SDM*, 3(1), 1–6.
- [60] Riggio, R. E. (2013). *Introduction to Industrial/Organizational Psychology (6th ed.)*. Pearson Education.
- [61] Rivai, Veithzal. (2008). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Untuk Perusahaan: dari Teori dan Praktik*. Jakarta: Grafindo Persada.
- [62] Robbins, S. P. & Judge, T. A. (2009). *Organizational Citizenship Behavior*. 13 Three Edition, USA: Pearson International Edition, Prentice-Hall.
- [63] Robbins, S. P. & Judge, T. A. (2016). *Prilaku Organisasi Edisi 16*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- [64] Robbins, S. P. (2001). *Perilaku Organisasi: Konsep, Kontroversi, Aplikasi*, Jilid 1, Edisi 8. Prenhallindo, Jakarta.
- [65] Robbins, Stephen P. dan Coulter, M. (2010). *Manajemen*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [66] Robbins, Stephen. P. (1996). *Perilaku Organisasi: Konsep, Kontroversi, Aplikasi*. Alih bahasa: Hadyana. Preinhallindo, Jakarta.
- [67] Romadhoni, L. C. Asnomy, T. & Suryatni, M. (2015). "Pengaruh beban kerja, lingkungan kerja, dan dukungan sosial terhadap stress kerja pustakawan di Kota Mataram". *Jurnal Ilmu Perpustakaan, Informasi, Dan Kearsipan*, 3(2), 125-145.
- [68] Sasono, E. (2004). "Mengelola Stres Kerja". *Jurnal Fokus Ekonomi*, 3(2), 305-320.
- [69] Siddhartha, V. & Malika, CSS. (2016). "Telecommuting and its effects in urban planning". *International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology (IJERT)*, 5(10).
- [70] Suarlan. (2017). "Teleworking for Indonesian Civil Servants: Problems and Actos". *International Journal of Administrative Science and Organization*, 100-109.
- [71] Sugiyono, D. (2013). *Metode penelitian pendidikan pendekatan kuantitatif, kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: PT. Alfabet.

- [72] Suliyanto, P. (2018). *Metode Penelitian Bisnis untuk Skripsi. Tesis & Disertasi*. Yogyakarta: Andi Publisher.
- [73] Tews, M. J. Gudmundson, A. & Skarlicki, D. P. (2014). "Telecommuting and work stress: The role of Boundary Control". *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 99(4), 739-747.
- [74] Thulin, E., Vilhelmson, B., & Johansson, M. (2019). New Telework, time pressure, and time use control in everyday life. *Sustainability*, 11(11), 3067.
- [75] Tong, S. T. & Walther, B. J. (2010). "Just Say "No Thanks": Romantic Rejection in Computer-Mediated Communication". *Journal of Social and Personal Relationships*, 27(3), 1-19.
- [76] Torraco, R. J. (2005). "Work Design Theory: A Review and Critique with Implications for Human Reseource Development". *Human Resources Development Quarterly*, 16(1), 85-109.
- [77] Uchenna, O. Uruakpa, P. C. & Uche, E. (2018). "Impact of Telecommuting on Employees Performance: A Focus on Telecommunication Out-Fits in Owerri, Imo State". *Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*, 9(2), 54-61.
- [78] Wambui, M. L., Cherotich, B. C., Emily, T., & Dave, B. (2017). Effects of Work-life Balance on Employees Performance in Institutions of Higher Learning. A Case Study of Kabarak University. *Kabarak Journal of Research & Innovation*, 4(2), 6079.
- [79] Wang, X. Huang, L. Liu, X. & Liu, W. (2021). "The challenges of Teleworkers during the COVID-19 pandemic: The impact on performance and well-being". *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 106(3), 437-451.
- [80] Wibowo, (2017). *Manajemen Kinerja. Edisi Kelima*. Depok: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada.
- [81] Ye, L. R. (2012). "Telecommuting: Implementation for Success". *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(20), 20-29.
- [82] Yoder, D. E. & Staudohar, P. D. (1982). "Attitudes towards unions: A review and research agenda". *Journal of Management*, 8(2), 7-22.